

nite_aura: an audio-visual Interactive immersive installation

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Biographical information

Jinsil Seo and Greg Corness are PhD candidates and interactive art instructors at the School of Interactive Arts and Technology at the Surrey campus of Simon Fraser University in Canada. Seo holds an MFA (Computer Art) from the School of Visual Arts in New York; she creates Media Art works that interlace space with human body and mind as artistic matter. Seo's artworks have been exhibited in the U.S., Canada, and Korea. Her research has been presented and published at numerous art and technology conferences. Corness holds a Masters degree in Music Composition from the University of Victoria and has composed a wide diversity of interactive works for Dance and Theatre.

Description of Piece

Figure 1. In side of nite_aura

the end of a fiber optic thread trying to fly off. When participants touch the grains of light, they fluctuate and swirl, and are separated from the physical end of fiber optics and illusory light traces become visible.

Granular synthesis and a set of resonant filters tuned to the harmonics of a bell are all controlled by the motion of the structure to produce the sound environment. The sounds made by each participant are recorded into an archive which contributes to this sonic ecosystem.

nite_aura is an audio-visual interactive installation exploring physical, auditory and visual motion within an immersive environment. Many children imagine themselves flying through a night sky full of stars. Humans often whisper wishes to the stars. *nite_aura* embodies these memories and experiences allowing for visitors to whisper to the air and play with fields of stars surrounding them.

The main structure is a hanging bell constructed of fiber optics and fabric. Participants enter the space by lifting one side, setting the bell in motion. Physical engagement is sustained by pulling cords from the ceiling or touching the glowing fiber optics that protrude into the bell surrounding the participant. The inside of the installation acts as a metaphor for private space, connecting infinite space and finite being, and acting as a pathway between sensual and virtual worlds.

Organic patterns based on the bell's swing influence grains of light and sound to immerse the viewers.

nite_aura's lights are soft and calm. Light affects our perception of emotion. Once the bell starts moving, points of light gently oscillate under the control of the participants; it seems that they are dancing in